

Ecological interactions among *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strains: insight into the complex dominance phenomenon

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Supplementary Table 1. Functional categories of genes significantly altered at least in two time points in mixed (A) and singles cultures (B) dominant strain versus non-dominant strain comparisons.

(A)				
Function	FDR	Genes in network	Genes in genome	
structural constituent of cell wall	0.0022384725191035206		4	12
(B)				
Function	FDR	Genes in network	Genes in genome	
RNA-directed DNA polymerase activity	2,27E-52		34	45
DNA polymerase activity	1,71E-45		34	61
DNA-directed DNA polymerase activity	1,41E-42		33	59
retrotransposon nucleocapsid	2,27E-38		34	89
ribonuclease activity	5,40E-36		33	89
transposition, RNA-mediated	1,44E-34		34	105
transposition	3,86E-34		34	108
nuclease activity	1,12E-32		35	135
nucleotidyltransferase activity	1,12E-32		34	118
peptidase activity	2,97E-28		33	135
hydrolase activity, acting on ester bonds	1,37E-20		35	281